

VALUE OF THE MICROMORPHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF THE DENTIN OF A TOOTH LOCATED UNDER AN ARTIFICIAL CROWN

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Introduction: Morphological changes in dentin under artificial crowns were studied on demineralized teeth 40-35 removed for medical reasons in a 61-year-old patient. When studying the microstructure of dentin in the presence of carious lesions, uniform mineralization of dentin tubules is detected in 20% of cases, in the presence of caries in 80% of cases, the irregular shape of dentin in the absence of caries can be determined visually in 45% of cases, in the absence of % of cases. Study of the structure of predentin in caries lesions, predentin dystrophy and destruction of calculus cells were found in 55% of cases, in the study of microparticles of teeth not susceptible to caries, predentin and calculus dystrophy were found in 70% of cases.

Keywords: caries, dentin, dental hard tissue, demineralized teeth, changes in dentin morphology, artificial crown.

Annotation: The formation of dentin in dental tissues occurs continuously, often at different rates, depending on the activity of functional or pathological stimuli. As a result, different types of dentin are formed in the dentin and dental pulp [1-3]. Conventional replacement dentin has almost the same structure as conventional dentin, differing only in the orientation of the dentin tubules, collagen fibers of the matrix and the degree of mineralization. It is called physiological dentin, since it is formed in response to functional stimuli. Inadequate replacement dentin is formed under the influence of active stimuli, such as acute caries, oral preparation, tooth preparation. Irregular secondary dentin has fewer dentin channels

and its orientation is more curved. This type of secondary dentin is usually formed by the pulp directly at the site of stimulation. The formation of irregular dentin is called tertiary dentin [2, 4]. The deposition of new dentin layers, which reduces the size of the dental pulp, occurs continuously throughout life and can only occur in the absence of inflammation in the dental pulp. [5] If the dental pulp is damaged as a result of surgical intervention, some tooth pockets die and the morphology of dentin becomes less regular (irregular and regenerates). The formation of reparative dentin creates an effective mechanism for protecting the pulp [1,5,6]. The first reaction of the pulp occurs when the drug enters the dentin from the enamel. The end of the tooth germ process occurs with a layer of solid dentin, which first forms mainly dentin around the tubule, and then mineralizes the tooth germ process. In the presence of superficial flat defects, a small amount of tertiary dentin is formed, and the layer of the dental bladder is reduced [7-13]. With age, certain changes occur in dentin: hardening of the primary dentin tubules, deposition of secondary dentin, formation of reparative dentin. In mature teeth, about 30% of the dentin tubules can be coated with mineralizers. The dentin tubules of the primary dentin are only gradually mineralized, maintaining the pockets in the living tooth. The distal end of the Toms filament can first form a small portion of tubular dentin in the dentin tubule, and then completely close the cavity. At the same time, the mineralization of dentin around the mouth increases significantly. Dentin sclerosis occurs not only with individual age, but also in response to long-term external stimuli, such as ablation, erosion and erosion. If the tooth bladder degenerates, there are no protozoa that inhabit the dentin canals and make the "way of death" [1, 14]. The above data served as the impetus for laboratory studies to determine the features of morphological visualization of hard dental tissues under artificial crowns. The aim was to evaluate the morphological characteristics of dentin under artificial crowns. The pathophysiological changes of dentin under artificial crowns were studied with materials and methods. 40-35 demineralized teeth were taken

according to medical indications during outpatient hospitalization from 20 main groups consisting of 61 removed teeth covered with caries-destroying artificial crowns. The comparison group consisted of 20 teeth that were removed without damaging the carious teeth, 10 of which were removed without damaging the carious teeth. They were under non-removable orthopedic structures. The tests lasted a total of 150 microseconds. The process of demineralized batches consists of the stages of consolidation, demineralization, dehydration, mass production and painting. Study of dental microscopic preparations and production of microphotographs are carried out using a DMLS microscope together with software (Leica, Germany). Analysis of the types of distribution features and their correspondence with the laws of normal distribution is carried out using the kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk criteria: homogeneous, soft interstitial basic substance ("enlightened" areas of dentin); wide tubular substance of "light" dentin; wide sections of longitudinal dentin canals, wavy or S-shaped intertubular substance, expanded, slightly homogeneous or micronized, light homogeneous; mineralization with slightly expanded strips of matrix. These areas are the result of hyperplasia of normal dentin of a heterogeneous type: between the pulp cavities - thinning of the dentin, its homogeneity; in the foci and in the root segments - pronounced and uneven thickening (hyperplasia), as well as marginal dentin with excess and mainly demyelination of the dentin tubules. Outside the above changes, and throughout the entire thickness of the tooth, the dentin (crown, neck and root) is mostly uniformly light, with uniformly weak and pronounced mineralization of the dentin tubules. Morphological examination of microscopic preparations of teeth without visually detectable caries revealed in 10% of cases a single superficial "open" carious cavity along the outer edge of the cervical dentin, in 20% - superficial "closed" carious cavities on the sides of the cervical and root dentin (Fig. 3). Surface erosion of the sides of the root dentin: small foci of dystrophic and lumpy caries with erosion of the marginal (peripheral) dentin and the formation of

mild demyelination. Superficial caries in the lateral regions of the cervical dentin: dystrophy with the formation of surface erosions and small foci of dentin caries, the edges and bottom of which are upright and represented by hypermineralized carious dentin. Peripheral focal dentin in the form of heterogeneously wide bands with hypo-, hyper- and demyelination of the dentin tubules, their thickening examination of microscopic preparations of teeth with visually detectable caries (Fig. 1). 4) that were under artificial crowns revealed that in 80% of cases the enamel was missing, in 20% the cervical segments of enamel were preserved. A study of caries-free teeth covered with orthopedic crowns showed that in half of the observations (50%) the crown enamel was partially preserved. The difference between the groups by the criteria of enamel was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 20,000a$; $DF = 2RP$). When studying the microscopic structure of dentin in the presence of carious lesions, it was found that homogeneous mineralization of dentin tubules occurred in 20% of cases, focal hypermineralization – 20%, focal demineralization – 15%, focal hypermineralization and simultaneous focal demineralization – 45% of observations. Similar mineralization of dentin tubules was observed in the absence of visually detectable decay in 80% of cases. Focal hypermineralization and demineralization occurred in 20% of observations. The difference between the frequency distribution of mineralization of dentin tubules and the presence of carious cavities was found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 10.636a$; $DF = 3p = 0.014$ according to Pearson's criterion). Irregular dentin in the presence of caries was found in 45% of cases, in 30% of cases, in the absence of carious lesions. The difference in the frequency distribution of irregular dentin detection was statistically unreliable (according to Fisher's correction and Pearson's criterion with $\chi^2 = 0.625B$, $DF = 1$, $P = 0.350$). Studying pathomorphological images of carious teeth under artificial crowns, it was found that in 20% of cases the composition of predentin did not change, in 10% of cases predentin and odontoblastic dystrophy was detected, predentin hypertrophy and odontoblastic elimination – 15%,

predantin dystrophy and odontoblastic elimination – 55%. Studying microscopic preparations of teeth without visually detectable caries, the composition of predantin did not change in 10% of cases, predantin and odontoblastic dystrophy was detected in 70%, predantin hypertrophy and odontoblastic elimination was detected in 20%. The difference in the frequency distribution of predentin structure detection based on the presence of degradation was statistically significant (according to Pearson's criterion with $\chi^2 = 14,000a$; $DF = 3$, $P = 0.003$). Conclusions:1. In the presence of carious lesions, it was found that in the absence of visually detectable caries, similar mineralization of the dental tube occurred in 80% of cases ($P=0.014$) compared with 20% of cases.2. The composition of predentin in teeth under artificial crowns with visually detectable caries was unchanged in 20% of cases, predentin and odontoblastic dystrophy was detected in 10%, predentin hypertrophy and odontoblastic elimination was detected in 15%, and predentin dystrophy and odontoblastic elimination was detected in 55%.In teeth without caries under the crown, the composition of predentin was unchanged in 10% of cases, predentin and odontoblastic dystrophy was detected in 70%, and predentin hypertrophy and odontoblastic elimination was detected in 20% of cases ($P=0.003$). 3. Microscopic changes in marginal and peripheral sections of dentin, at the bottom of the carious cavity and in the proximal part of the root canal were established depending on the location of the carious cavity, the prevalence of the carious process and the distal proportion of carious destruction.

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